

Obstacles to implementing innovative ideas in the educational field

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Abstract

Innovative approaches often require collaboration between educators, administrators, and other stakeholders. However, silos and competing interests can make collaboration difficult. Schools can foster a culture of collaboration by creating opportunities for teachers and administrators to work together, sharing best practices, and encouraging cross-functional teams.

Key words

Collaboration, citizens' knowledge, professional development, technology

Introduction

Creating new things, generating new insights, taking risk is not easy all the time in every sphere and educational field is not exception. According to famous researchers: Innovations in education are of particular importance because education plays a crucial role in creating a sustainable future. “Innovation resembles mutation, the biological process that keeps species evolving so they can better compete for survival” (Hoffman and Holzhter, 2012, p. 3). So innovation is considered as a necessary instrument and positive change. As I have been in this sphere for more than ten years I can find some obstacles which prevent us from innovating new methods in education.

Firstly, obtaining new changes and innovations in every field depends on citizens' knowledge in terms of social and economic issues because there is big demand for high skill profiles and high level of knowledge by prestigious organizations. Educators need to be provided with training and support to help them understand the benefits of innovative approaches and how they can be implemented effectively.

Even when an innovation comes to life, it is of little worth without implementation (Csikszentmihalyi, 2013). Innovation is not about talking the talk but walking the walk. it is said that Today's education systems are required to be

both effective and efficient, or in other words, to reach the goals set for them while making the best use of available resources” (Cornali, 2012, p. 255) . In order to show sizable result we need an army of implementers who have creativity and motivated skills to do their best in the implementation. It should be taken environment into account while creators working they should feel freedom , security on the job to take risks, and control of what they are doing

Secondly, although today’s world is considered the century of technology many schools and students may not have access to the latest technology, making it difficult to implement innovative approaches that rely on digital tools. William Massy and Robert Zemsky wrote in their paper, “Using Information Technology to Enhance Academic Productivity,” that “[...] technology should be used to boost academic productivity” (Massy and Zemsky, 1995). I think the best solution to this problem can be that schools can partner with technology companies to provide access to devices and software, or they can explore low-tech solutions that still promote innovation and creativity.

Another reason why Innovation is becoming difficult in education system is that many educators may be comfortable with traditional teaching methods and may be hesitant to adopt new techniques. Creating new rules and methods disrupt the established routine and pushes implementers out of their comfort zone. Terry Heick writes that “[...] many schools give lip-service to the concept of innovation in mission statements, on websites, in PDs (professional development), and during committee, council, and board meetings, but lose their nerve when it’s time to make it happen.

Four approaches easing innovation in the implementation.

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